

LF damage in Kerala, India, 1983-85.

Control of LF resurgence on variety Annapoorna. Kerala, India, 1983-85.

Insecticide	Application method	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Damaged leaves ^a (%)		
			29 DT ^b	44 DT ^c	60 DT
Chlorpyrifos 20 EC	Foliar	0.5	17.9	14.9	2.7
Quinalphos 25 EC	Foliar	0.5	18.3	6.7	0.6
Carbofuran 3 G	Soil	0.75	7.3	56.5	72.5
Quinalphos 5 G	Soil	0.75	10.4	50.6	52.5
Phorate 10 G	Soil	0.75	10.6	34.4	45.2
Monocrotophos 40 EC	Foliar	0.5	14.7	10.3	3.4
No insecticide (untreated control)	-	-	17.7	65.8	70.0

^aComputed from 25 infested hills in each treatment. Insecticides applied 30 and 45 DP. ^b1 d before first application. ^c1 d before second application.

concentrate) and granular insecticide formulations applied at 30 and 45 DT. The results confirmed that, in general, granular insecticide formulations are less effective than EC formulations (see table).

Carbofuran had controlled LF earlier, but resurgence was evident recently. Samples of LF larvae were collected from ricefields and reared in the laboratory. Adults that emerged were identified by wing markings. Adults collected from light traps also were identified.

An estimate for 3 mo Oct to Dec showed that about 50% of the LF population was *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley, which had not been reported in this region before. The rest of the population was common LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée. □

Occurrence and infectivity of entomogenous nematodes in mole crickets in Brazil

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In certain regions of the Amazon, mole crickets of the genera *Scapteriscus* and *Neocurtilla* are major pests of rice planted on seasonal floodplains. Although nematodes have been isolated previously from Brazilian mole crickets, work since 1982 on natural enemies has revealed 18 isolates of *Steinernema felitae* (Filipjev) (*Neoaplectana carpocapsae* Weiser) and 13 isolates of *Heterorhabditis* sp. from 1,532 site collections.

Site collections consist of digging mole crickets from each sampled locality and field. Site collections ranged from 1 to more than 500 crickets.

In initial laboratory evaluations, it was impossible to propagate the nematodes on the wax moths *Galleria* sp. usually used for mass production. We screened mole crickets that had been held in the laboratory at least 30 d to ensure they were not infested with nematodes or other pathogenic agents and exposed them to nematodes on

moist filter paper in petri plates. A minimum 50% mortality was obtained from all isolates, and at least 70% for *S. felitae* isolates. There was no mortality in untreated crickets.

In tests using the same methods with other lepidoptera and hymenoptera, such as honey bees and ants, mortality was less than 10%. Using the methods with field crickets *Gryllus* sp. and short-tailed crickets *Anurogryllus* sp. gave infectivity rates in excess of 50%.

These results indicate that these nematode strains are highly host-specific and extremely infective to mole, field, and short-tailed crickets. As these strains were isolated from sandy riverbanks and from mole cricket populations, their potential use for the major pest species of the Amazon, *Scapteriscus didactylus* Scudder, as well as for locally troublesome species of mole crickets seems highly promising, especially in the Amazon, where mole cricket densities are high, and there are no registered control insecticides. □

Neem seed kernel or neem cake powder and carbofuran granule mixture for controlling green leafhopper (GLH) and rice tungro virus (RTV)

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Carbofuran granules at 2 kg ai/ha are often applied as a prophylactic measure to rice in RTV-prone areas. Insecticidal control relying on economic threshold levels for the vector GLH *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) is risky.

Neem seed derivatives have been found to reduce GLH feeding and RTV transmission. They reportedly possess antimicrobial activity that may reduce the degradation of carbofuran in flooded rice soils.

We tested neem seed kernel and neem cake powder mixed with carbofuran at 1 kg ai/ha (33.3 kg neem powder: 33.3 kg Furadan 3G) against carbofuran

Mortality of GLH adults, nymph emergence, and RTV infection in TN1 plants treated with carbofuran mixed with neem seed kernel (NSK) or neem cake (NC) powder or with carbofuran alone.^a IIRRI, 1987.

Treatment	Adult mortality (%) in infestations		Nymphs emerged (no.)	RTV infection (%)
	1st	2d		
Carbofuran (1 kg ai/ha) + NSK (1:1)	100 a	100 a	0 a	2 a
Carbofuran (1 kg ai/ha) + NC (1:1)	98 a	96 a	0 a	8 b
Carbofuran (2 kg ai/ha)	100 a	100 a	0 a	10 b
Carbofuran (1 kg ai/ha)	100 a	98 a	4 b	28 c
Untreated (control)	0 b	0 b	285 c	100 d

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. Av of 5 replications.

at 2 kg ai/ha (66.6 kg Furadan 3G). Because neem trees are widespread in many rice-growing countries, neem-carbofuran mixtures could appreciably reduce the cost of purchased inputs for RTV management.

Powdered neem seed kernel and cake from 1987 harvest were mixed separately (1:1 wt/wt) with carbofuran in polythene bags. The neem-carbofuran mix or carbofuran alone was applied at 2 kg ai/ha to 1-mo-old potted GLH- and RTV-susceptible TN1 rice plants. Untreated plants and plants treated with carbofuran at 1 kg ai/ha were the controls.

At 24 h after treatment, 5 pairs of viruliferous GLH males and females were caged on treated and control plants. Insect mortality was measured

72 h after infestation and used GLH adults were removed and replaced with 5 pairs of fresh viruliferous adults. Insect mortality was measured 72 h after reinfestation. Nymph emergence was observed daily from 1 wk after first infestation to 10 d after reinfestation. RTV infection based on visual symptoms was measured 20 d after reinfestation.

Insect mortality was 98-100% with carbofuran alone, 96-100% in the neem-carbofuran mixtures, and 0 in the control (see table). Nymph emergence in the carbofuran treatments significantly differed from that in the control. Carbofuran mixed with neem seed kernel powder was most effective against RTV, keeping infection to 2%. □

Sensitivity of different stages of *Leptocorisa oratorius* (Fabricius) to monocrotophos

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Nymphs and adults of *L. oratorius*, the most widely distributed rice bug species, damage rice from flowering through the dry dough stage. A common control method is the use of insecticides. To be more efficient, insecticide should be applied not only at the stage when the pests do the most damage to rice, but also when the insects are most sensitive to the treatment. We tested five nymphal instars and female adults to

LD₅₀, values for reaction of different life stages of *Leptocorisa oratorius* to monocrotophos. IIRRI, 1987.

Stage	LD ₅₀ ^a	
	µg/g	µg/insect
First instar	0.52 c	0.70 a
Second instar	0.62 c	1.70 b
Third instar	0.56 c	4.85 c
Fourth instar	0.89 d	16.24 e
Fifth instar	0.37 b	39.11 f
Adult female	0.06 a	9.13 d

^aLD₅₀s followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

determine the insect stage most sensitive to insecticides.

Insects collected in vials from culture cages were anaesthetized with CO₂.